

POTENTIALS OF IMMUNOTROPIC THERAPY IN THE COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT OF NEWBORN INFANTS WITH HERPESVIRUS INFECTIONS

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Abstract. *Objective of the research is to study cytokine production in newborns with herpesvirus infections in the context of basic and immunotropic therapy. 119 newborns with herpesvirus infections were examined: Group 1 - control (30); Group 2 - children examined before treatment (35); Group 3 - children receiving traditional therapy (28); Group 4 - newborns receiving Likopid (26). The levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α in serum were studied before and after treatment in both sick and healthy newborns in a comparative aspect. Cytokine concentration was determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Clinical and statistical studies were conducted. It was established that after the use of the drug Likopid, the elevated levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α significantly decreased to 227.5 \pm 5.77 pg/ml, 22.1 \pm 1.15 pg/ml, and 27.4 \pm 1.33 pg/ml, respectively, which was statistically significant compared to the group of children receiving traditional therapy ($P < 0.001$). Cytokine levels in newborns after the inclusion of Likopid in the basic therapy did not show statistically significant differences compared to control values. A pronounced clinical-immunological effect was obtained.*

Keywords: *newborn, herpesvirus infections, cytokines, immunotropic therapy.*

One of the leading problems in modern perinatology is intrauterine infections, among which herpesvirus infections hold a special place [1,9,11]. They are highly prevalent, tend to have a prolonged course, can affect women's reproductive health, and are a common cause of preterm births, stillbirths, disability, and high mortality among premature infants [3,5].

According to some data, the prevalence of HSV-1 in the population in various countries ranges from 90%-95%, HSV-2 reaches up to 20%-30%, and CMV is detected in 80%-100% of the population [4,13].

It is known that the development of the infectious process is determined not only by the virulence of the pathogen but also by the immune status of the newborn. Immune system development in the neonatal period faces certain challenges, and in cases of intrauterine infections, the immunological reactivity of newborns undergoes significant changes in all immune system components [1,8,14]. Some studies suggest that in congenital infections, particularly CMV infections, there is an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-8, TNF- α , and a decrease in IL-1 β [7,12]. Other studies have shown that in intrauterine generalized CMV infection, there is a decrease in IFN- α , IFN- γ levels, and an increase in IL-6, IL-8, and MCR-1 levels [8].

This largely determines the fact that intrauterine infections are a frequent cause of severe perinatal pathology and fatalities, making the treatment of newborns with intrauterine infections a

priority for optimization. Given that some antiviral medications are highly toxic and not approved for use in newborns, an important reserve for treating and preventing the development of intrauterine infections in newborns is rational immune correction [10]. However, modern immunopathogenetic therapeutic agents should be used with caution, considering the limitations related to the age-specific characteristics of the newborn's immune system.

Objective of the study: To study cytokine production in newborns with herpesvirus infections in the context of basic and immunotropic therapy.

Materials and methods: Clinical studies were conducted at the GDKB No. 5 in Tashkent. Immunological studies of the observed newborns were conducted at the laboratory of immune regulation at the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In total, 119 newborns with various clinical manifestations of combined infections (CMV + HSV) were examined. The observed newborns with intrauterine infections were divided into four groups: Group 1 - control (n=30); Group 2 - children examined before treatment (n=35); Group 3 - children receiving traditional comprehensive therapy (n=28); Group 4 - newborns receiving Likopid (n=26).

The control group consisted of healthy newborns born to healthy mothers with uncomplicated pregnancies and physiological deliveries.

The levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin-1 beta, interleukin-6, and tumor necrosis factor-alpha (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α) in serum were studied and analyzed before and after treatment in both sick and healthy newborns for comparison.

The concentration of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α was determined using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) with the test systems from "VECTOR-BEST" (Russia, Novosibirsk). Quantitative evaluation of results was performed by constructing a calibration curve or using the commercial software "MicroplateManager," reflecting the optical density as a function of antigen concentration for standard samples and allowing comparison with the studied samples. Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica 6.0 software. The significance of differences in means between the compared groups was assessed using the Student's t-test.

Results and Discussion: This study provides a comprehensive clinical-immunological assessment of the effectiveness of adding the drug Likopid to basic therapy in newborns with combined HSV and CMV infections.

Likopid is a synthetic analog of the main fragment of peptidoglycan from the cell wall of all known bacteria (glucosaminylmuramyl-dipeptide - GMDP), which has a broad effect on the immune system, stimulating the functional activity of phagocytes and enhancing the proliferation of T and B lymphocytes. Likopid is approved for use in newborns [6]. Likopid was administered to newborns at a dose of 0.5 mg (1/2 tablet) twice a day for 10 days, starting from the first week of life. Likopid was dissolved in 5-10 ml of boiled water and administered orally with a spoon, pacifier, or feeding tube 20-30 minutes before feeding. During the observation period, no side effects were detected while using the Likopid therapy.

Comprehensive treatment was carried out in accordance with the clinical situation, including antiviral, antibacterial, metabolic therapy, and correction of hemostasis and detoxification therapy. For antiviral therapy, acyclovir and Viferon were used.

We studied cytokine production in newborns with CMV + HSV infections before and after treatment over a 2-week period (Table 1). The data we obtained showed that cytokine production was significantly altered in combined herpesvirus infections. Specifically, the production of IL-

1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α in the sick children was statistically significantly increased (723.5 \pm 22.80 pg/ml, 74.8 \pm 2.88 pg/ml, and 81.2 \pm 3.66 pg/ml, P<0.001), compared to control values of 194.7 \pm 8.17 pg/ml, 12.9 \pm 0.59 pg/ml, and 17.1 \pm 0.74 pg/ml, respectively.

After traditional treatment, the production of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α significantly decreased to 495.5 \pm 15.86 pg/ml, 49.5 \pm 3.92 pg/ml, and 63.5 \pm 4.14 pg/ml, respectively, compared to pre-treatment levels, but remained significantly higher than the control values (P<0.001).

Table 1.

Cytokine concentration levels in newborns with combined herpesvirus infections after treatment.

Immunological indicatots	Healthy newborns (control) (n=30)	Before treatment (n=35) CMV + HSV	Traditional treatment (n=28)	Likopid (n=26)
IL-1 β , pg/ml	194,7 \pm 8,17	723,5 \pm 22,80*	495,5 \pm 15,86	\wedge 227,5 \pm 5,77
IL-6, pg/ml	12,9 \pm 0,59	74,8 \pm 2,88*	49,5 \pm 3,92	\wedge 22,1 \pm 1,15
TNF- α , pg/ml	17,1 \pm 0,74	81,2 \pm 3,66*	63,5 \pm 4,14	\wedge 27,4 \pm 1,33

Note: Statistically significant compared to the control group (*-P<0.001); \wedge - Statistically significant compared to traditional treatment (\wedge -P<0.001).

It was found that after the application of the drug Likopid, the concentration of IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α significantly decreased to 227.5 \pm 5.77 pg/ml, 22.1 \pm 1.15 pg/ml, and 27.4 \pm 1.33 pg/ml, respectively, showing a statistically significant difference compared to the group of children receiving traditional therapy (P<0.001). The cytokine levels in newborns after including Likopid in the basic therapy did not show statistically significant differences from the control values.

In the next phase of our work, we conducted an analysis of the clinical effectiveness of Likopid as part of complex therapy. The clinical effectiveness of Likopid was assessed based on an analysis of several indicators that characterize the clinical condition of the child: duration of respiratory therapy, duration of the child's stay in a critical condition, onset of stable weight gain, duration of fever, and length of stay in the hospital. As our research showed, the overwhelming majority of children with herpesvirus infections were born to mothers with unfavorable obstetric histories, complicated pregnancies, and difficult deliveries.

Table 2.

Clinical effectiveness of Likopid in newborns with intrauterine herpesvirus infections

Parameters	Traditional treatment (n=28)	Likopid (n=26)	P – difference validity
Long-term respiratory therapy, % of children	82,1 \pm 7,2	53,8 \pm 9,8	P1/2<0,001
Duration of the child's stay in critical condition, days	20,7 \pm 0,4	14,2 \pm 0,3	P1/2<0,001
Duration of fever, days	16,5 \pm 0,7	9,2 \pm 0,5	P1/2<0,001
Onset of stable weight gain, days	19,3 \pm 0,4	11,7 \pm 0,5	P1/2 <0,001
Reduction in the size of the liver and spleen (on which day)	17,2 \pm 0,6	12,3 \pm 0,3	P1/2 <0,001

Duration of hospital stay, days	36,3±0,8	24,2±0,6	P1/2<0,001
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Note - P – the significance of differences between group 1 and group 2

Intrauterine development of the fetus often occurred against the background of chronic intrauterine hypoxia, fetoplacental insufficiency, and infectious-inflammatory pathology in the mother. The children were more often born in asphyxia, so a significant number of them required respiratory support. The obtained data showed that the use of Likopid in complex therapy for newborns with herpesvirus infections demonstrated a high level of therapeutic effectiveness across all studied parameters. In our research, 82.1±7.2% of newborns receiving traditional therapy required prolonged respiratory support. Among children receiving immunocorrective therapy, the number of such newborns was significantly lower and amounted to 53.8±9.8% (Table 2).

A significant proportion of children were admitted to the neonatal pathology department in critical condition, with the severity of the condition caused by morphofunctional immaturity, severe central nervous system damage, and damage to other organs and systems. The severity of the newborn's condition largely depends on the state of the body's defense mechanisms. We conducted an analysis of the duration of stay in critical condition. It was found that newborns on traditional therapy remained in critical condition for 20.7±0.4 days. However, newborns receiving Likopid as part of complex therapy recovered from the critical state faster, and this period was reduced to 14.2±0.3 days.

One important indicator of the infectious-inflammatory process in the child was the increase in temperature. In newborns with herpesvirus infections receiving basic therapy, the duration of elevated temperature lasted for 16.5±0.7 days. For newborns receiving Likopid as part of complex therapy, this period was shortened to 9.2±0.5 days.

Another key indicator of improving the child's condition during clinical observation was the increase in body weight. In our studies, we analyzed from which day after therapy a stable weight gain occurred. It was found that when Likopid was included in the complex therapy of newborns, stable weight gain occurred significantly earlier (from day 11.7±0.5) compared to children on traditional therapy (from day 9.2±0.5).

Also, in our studies, a significant number of children, as mentioned earlier, exhibited hepatosplenomegaly. In newborns receiving Likopid, the reduction in the size of the liver and spleen occurred earlier—by day 12.3±0.3, compared to traditional therapy, where it took until day 17.2±0.6.

Follow-up of newborns in dynamics also showed that children receiving Likopid in complex therapy showed regression of neurological symptoms more quickly, with faster reduction of hyperexcitability syndrome and CNS depression. The use of Likopid in complex therapy also contributed to a faster normalization of functional indicators in the cardiovascular and respiratory systems. All of this led to an improvement in the condition of newborns and a reduction in hospital stay duration. Thus, the average length of stay for newborns receiving traditional treatment was 36.3±0.8 days, while including Likopid in the treatment of children with herpesvirus infections reduced this period to 24.2±0.6 days.

Thus, the results of our studies demonstrated that the use of Likopid, which has antiviral and immunomodulatory effects, as part of complex therapy for newborns with herpesvirus infections, leads to a pronounced clinical and immunological effect. The increased production of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1β, IL-6, TNF-α in newborns with combined herpesvirus

infections (CMV+HSV) decreased significantly after treatment with Likopid, leading to a significant improvement in clinical symptoms.

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